

Constitution of Embelin.

BY KRISHNA SHRINIVAS NARGUND AND BALVANT WASUDEV BHIDE.

Heffter and Feuerstein (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1900, 238, 15) showed that embelin contained a side-chain, very probably $C_{11}H_{23}$ as they were able to isolate *n*-lauric acid by oxidation. They prepared a dibenzoyl derivative and showed that embelin condenses with primary amines in the same way as benzoquinone. Moreover on reduction it gives a colourless dihydroembelin which quickly oxidises in air to embelin thus showing a behaviour akin to quinone. These facts led them to assign the constitutional formula (I) to embelin. One of us (K.S.N.) and Kanga (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1929, 145) proved the presence of two keto-groups in the molecule, while Kaul, Ray and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 577) observed that it behaved as if it had four keto-groups under certain conditions.

Kaul Ray and Dutt (*loc. cit.*), by oxidising embelin with fuming nitric acid, obtained isolauric acid which on further oxidation gave isocaproic acid. Heffter and Feuerstein (*loc. cit.*) isolated *n*-lauric acid by oxidising embelin with alkaline potassium permanganate. Oxidation of embelin, either by alkaline potassium permanganate or by potassium permanganate in acetone solution, yielded the same products as obtained by Heffter and Feuerstein. Indeed, the crude acid obtained by oxidation, does melt at $35-37^{\circ}$ as stated by Dutt and his colleagues but after a couple of crystallisations the melting point rises to 43.5° and is not diminished by the admixture of *n*-lauric acid, obtained from Kahlbaum. The oxidation of embelin under different conditions by dilute nitric acid has been very thoroughly studied by Limaye (*Proc. Indian Science Congress, Nagpur*, 1931). In addition to *n*-lauric acid he isolated *n*-lauronitrile but not isolauric acid.

A clue to the solution of this problem was afforded by the work of Fichter (*Annalen*, 1908, 361, 363) who prepared a number of *p*-dioxyquinones and studied their hydrolysis in detail ; under the conditions of experiments described by him he obtained disubstituted succinic acids. As there is a great resemblance between Fichter's

compounds and embelin we decided to study its hydrolysis. Embelin on hydrolysis by dilute sodium hydroxide gave α -ketomyristic acid, $C_{14}H_{26}O_3$, m.p. 63.8° (oxime, m.p. 95° ; semicarbazone, decom. above 170°). Its constitution was proved by its oxidation to tridecoic acid, m.p. 43° (zinc salt, m.p. 128°). The melting point was considerably lowered by mixing it with *n*-lauric acid. (Mrs.) Robinson describes tridecoic acid as melting at 43° , and the zinc salt at 128° (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 226). The mechanism of the formation of α -ketomyristic acid from embelin may be represented as follows:

Attempts were made to isolate α -ketobutyric acid (III) from the mother-liquor after separating the α -ketomyristic acid. In all cases a gum was obtained which could not be induced to crystallise from the usual solvents. We were also unable to isolate any crystalline compound after esterifying the gum.

The synthesis of embelin either from *p*-dihydroxychlorotoluquinone and undecyl chloride or from α -ketomyristic ester and α -ketobutyric ester is being attempted.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Embelin, m.p. 143° , used in this work was prepared by extracting the dry berries with ether followed by washing with petrol; one crystallisation from alcohol gave the pure product.

Oxidation of Embelin in Acetone Solution.—Embelin (5 g.) was dissolved in acetone (50 c.c.) and potassium permanganate (4 g.) added with stirring and cooling. The product was then diluted with water (50 c.c.) and a rapid stream of sulphur dioxide was passed

into it. The oil which separated out was removed by means of ether. After the removal of ether, a solid melting at $35\text{--}37^\circ$ was obtained. It was further crystallised from alcohol when it melted at $43\cdot5^\circ$ and was identical with *n*-lauric acid obtained from Kahlbaum. Oxidation of embelin by alkaline permanganate also gave the same product. The acid was also converted into lauramide, m.p. 98° .

Hydrolysis of Embelin and Isolation of α -Ketomyristic Acid.—Embelin (5 g.) was heated with aqueous potassium hydroxide (200 c.c. of 5 per cent.) on the water-bath for four hours. The original violet colour changed to brown. On cooling, sodium ketomyristate separated out which was filtered and washed with water. It can be crystallised from hot water as a fine micro-crystalline powder and is insoluble in cold water. (Found: Na, 9.1. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_3\text{Na}$ requires Na, 8.99 per cent.). Fichter recommends boiling till the solution becomes colourless. In one of our experiments even though the boiling was continued for 96 hours the product did not become colourless and the separation of α -ketomyristic acid became difficult. The sodium salt was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid and α -ketomyristic acid thus liberated was crystallised from light petrol as small plates, m.p. $63\cdot8^\circ$. The acid retains the solvent somewhat tenaciously and it is necessary to keep it in vacuum over paraffin for several hours to remove the last traces of the solvent. (Found: C, 69.3; H, 10.8; equivalent, 241. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 69.4; H, 10.74 per cent.; equivalent, 242).

Semicarbazone of α -Ketomyristic Acid.—The keto-acid (1.2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol and treated with semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.6 g.) and excess of sodium acetate. The mixture was warmed and the mixture for 24 hours. On diluting and acidifying, the semicarbazone separated as a flocculent precipitate. It is crystallised from dilute alcohol and decomposes above 170° . (Found: C, 60.08; H, 9.78; N, 13.8. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires C, 60.2; H, 9.7; N, 14.0 per cent.).

Oxime of α -Ketomyristic Acid.—The keto-acid (1.2 g.) was treated in alcoholic solution with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) and an excess of sodium acetate. After 24 hours the mixture was diluted with water and acidified. An oil (0.9 g.) separated which soon solidified. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in rosettes, m.p. $94\text{--}95^\circ$. (Found: N, 5.6. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 5.45 per cent.).

Oxidation of Ketomyristic Acid by Nitric Acid.—The acid (1.2 g.) was boiled with 35 c.c. of nitric acid (1:4) for 18 hours. Then 5 c.c. of fuming nitric acid were added and heating was continued for a further period of 5 hours. On cooling tridecoic acid (0.8 g.) solidified. On crystallising twice from dilute alcohol it melted at 43°. The zinc salt prepared by treating the ammonium salt with excess of zinc chloride, when crystallised twice from amyl alcohol, melted at 128°.

Oxidation of the Keto-acid by Alkaline Potassium Permanganate.—The keto-acid (1 g.) was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution (50 c.c. of 5 per cent.) and then treated with potassium permanganate (20 c.c. of 10 per cent.). It was heated on the water-bath for an hour. On filtering and acidifying an oil separated which quickly solidified. After crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 43°. The zinc salt had m.p. 128°.

In conclusion we have great pleasure in expressing our heartfelt thanks to Prof. Kanga and Mr. Limaye for their kind interest and advice during the progress of the work.

M. R. SCIENCE INSTITUTE, AHMEDABAD
AND
SIR PARASHURAMBHAU COLLEGE, POONA.

Received January 19, 1931.